

Assessing the Suitability of the All Science Journal
Classification for the Directory of Open Access Journals

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1 Introduction

The question of whether to provide open access to scientific journals is increasingly important as discussion is raised on the issue of knowledge as a public good and paywalls as an impediment to a free and informed society. The Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) has done a great deal to pave the way for open access journals to come to prominence. However, their current classification system limits them from providing the best access possible. This project aims to examine an alternate classification system for the DOAJ, assess its overall suitability, and provide a recommendation as to whether or not the DOAJ should adopt this new classification system. This project will look at the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) created by Elsevier and used in their Scopus database to determine its potential value to the DOAJ.

The DOAJ is a non-profit organisation that indexes a multitude of open access journals, across many countries and in many languages. They are committed to providing an index of high-quality journals that are open access, meaning there are no fees to access these journals. The DOAJ also provides access to all types of journals, no matter their scope or discipline. This way, every researcher has the potential to find a journal – no matter what they study. The DOAJ is completely independent and primarily receives its funding from public organisations, like libraries or universities (DOAJ, 2020b). In order to be listed in the DOAJ, a journal must meet specific, high standards (DOAJ, 2019). According to the DOAJ website, their users are mostly young people, most notably from North America, the United Kingdom, Indonesia, Australia, Brazil, and China (DOAJ, 2020a). The DOAJ is also used by researchers that wish to find a journal in which to publish their research. The DOAJ is currently using a truncated version of the Library of Congress Classification (LCC) system, and currently indexes over 18,000 journals, distributed across 19 main LCC classes, with classes E and F being grouped together.

There are a few reasons that this system is not optimal for the DOAJ's goals. Firstly, the LCC system is based on an American point-of-view, whereas the DOAJ wishes to promote journals from all over the world. For example, two classes in the LCC focus solely on the history of the Americas, whereas all other continents' histories are grouped into one class. Another issue with using an American-based system is that it is focused towards classifying English language publications, despite the DOAJ being multilingual. According to the DOAJ, reports of user dissatisfaction often stemmed from not being able to find a journal when searching in a language that was not English (DOAJ, 2020a). The LCC does not provide the level of granularity that the DOAJ needs, considering the diverse range of journals it houses. According to Dominic Mitchell, the Operations Manager at the DOAJ, the new classification system must be user-friendly, whether it be for finding articles or a journal in which to publish. The new system must also be machine-readable, for the purpose of using metadata. A new classification system should include global coverage, as well as being open source. It should also be easy to transfer the journals from the LCC classification into the new system.

The ASJC system was created by Elsevier in 2004 for their new database, Scopus (Schotten, el Aisati, Meester, Steinginga & Ross, 2018). The aim for Scopus was to create a

database that covered a multitude of scientific disciplines (Schotten et al., 2018). The ASJC system uses four broad categories: physical sciences, health sciences, social sciences & humanities, and life sciences. These are known as subject areas (Schotten et al., 2018). They are further divided into 27 subject area classifications and 334 subcategories (Elsevier, 2022 & Schotten et al., 2018). For the purposes of this report, a literature review will be performed in order to gain a better idea of the ASJC system and its potential suitability for the DOAJ. An evaluation of the ASJC system will be given by providing an analysis as well as mapping data from the old system to the new one. Furthermore, suitability for the DOAJ will be tested by reclassifying journals to the ASJC system as well as identifying journals indexed in Scopus and the DOAJ to assess the level of similarity in their respective classifications. Finally, a recommendation concerning the adoption of the ASJC system in place of the LCC will be made.

2 Literature review and environmental scan

There is a substantial body of literature addressing the question of how suitable the LCC scheme, currently used by the DOAJ, is for modern journal classification and critiquing its flaws. Likewise, there is a body of literature examining the successes and failures of Scopus and, to some degree, the ASJC by extension. While the published literature is insufficient to determine a consensus view on the ASJC, it still provides useful context for this report.

As established, the DOAJ is currently using a truncated version of the LCC scheme. The LCC has become widely popular in academic settings for myriad reasons. Firstly, it was one of the first strong, simple-yet-granular schemes that was not developed with overlong classmarks (Higgins, 2012). Additionally, the Library of Congress made their classification cards public for reuse, and to this day most materials that enter library circulation will already have an LCC class assigned (Higgins, 2012). As such, it is simple and efficient to use LCC in most academic settings.

However, the LCC was not created for global use and has been subject to significant criticism due to its American-centred bias. Developed between 1899 and 1903 (Howard & Knowlton, 2018), the LCC scheme is bound in biases from early 20th century America, where diversity was not a primary concern. Furthermore, the LCC was not developed with browsing in mind — less than 1% of the Library of Congress's collections are available for general browsing. Rather, the LCC was developed as a shelving guide for the Library of Congress (Higgins, 2012). The result is a classification scheme that has been misused because of its ease of use, but which in an increasingly diverse society does not function as a solution for contemporary global classifications. Additionally, the LCC classes do not handle multidisciplinary or interdisciplinary documents well (Howard & Knowlton, 2018). As more fields merge and interdisciplinarity becomes more common, the LCC becomes less effective at classifying documents accurately. It is pertinent, then, to consider a more contemporary approach to classification.

Developed by Elsevier in 2004 with the launch of their Scopus database (Pranckutė, 2021), ASJC offers a potential solution to the weaknesses of the LCC scheme. Since its inception, Scopus has become one of the two main sources of publication metadata today, alongside Web of Science (Pranckutė, 2021). Elsevier has used ASJC to classify over 40,000 journals in Scopus, from a broad range of countries and in a variety of languages. The ASJC is a classification system that functions at the journal level (Singh et al., 2020). There are 4 broad disciplines in the scheme: life sciences, health sciences, physical sciences, and social sciences and humanities. The ASJC also has class codes that are specifically geared toward multidisciplinary works. Journals that are multidisciplinary will, under ASJC, be indexed under 2 or more categories. In fact, the Scopus database regularly assigns multiple categories to single journals (Pranckutė, 2021).

Despite the benefits which the ASJC can offer, and which the LCC cannot — like assigning multiple topics and having temporal separation from the pronounced biases of the late nineteenth-century — the existing literature is clear on the fact that ASJC has flaws of its own. While the ability to assign multiple subjects to the same journal avoids the LCC's issue of inaccurately representing multidisciplinary publications, Scopus has been argued to be over-liberal in its assignment of multiple ASJC subjects to the same publication. In one particularly egregious instance, Scopus assigned a single publication to 27 ASJC categories — exactly as many as there are top-level categories in the ASJC system (Wang & Waltman, 2016). Given that ASJC was designed for Scopus, this does suggest that either Scopus is using the system poorly, or the ASJC system has granularity issues. This issue arises especially with regards to niche topics like “Decision Sciences” and “Chemical Engineering” (Gusenbauer, 2022). While the Scopus database —for which the ASJC was designed— is notably focused on engineering and manufacturing (Franceschini et al., 2016), both “Chemical Engineering” and “Materials Science” are only rarely the sole category for a publication (only about 10% of the time — a low level of uniqueness), whereas some categories, like “Medicine” and “Dentistry,” are the sole category for a publication more than two-thirds of the time (Gusenbauer, 2022) — a much higher level of uniqueness. This unevenness suggests that certain larger categories may benefit from further subdividing, and smaller, less unique categories, which lack precise keywords (Gusenbauer, 2022), could benefit from greater effort spent on delineating their boundaries such that literature which would otherwise fall primarily within its scope are not lost within larger categories.

Elsevier's lack of transparency as to how categories were chosen and the ASJC constructed overall (Wang & Waltman, 2016) makes identifying the underlying epistemological choices difficult. The LCC was not designed to make a comprehensive universal system of categorizing all potential topics. The shelving of materials in a single largely-private library was its purpose, and manifestly so (Higgins, 2012). While the ASJC has the theoretical benefit of surpassing this limitation-of-origin, as it is intended to be able to subsume any material within itself — not just that which was created for a specific library — it still bears many of the limitations of the Scopus system for which it was designed. Scopus works at a journal-level rather than an article-level, and at the article-level it has worse accuracy than competitors Dimensions and Web of Science (Singh et al., 2020). While this is

not theoretically a significant problem for the DOAJ, as it operates on a journal-level, it may help explain some of why the ASJC classification of niche topics is so uneven in its uniqueness and granularity. Domains like decision sciences are unlikely to be the entire scope of a journal, and thus almost any journal which contains them within its scope would likely have an alternate or additional category attached as well. It may then become difficult to find sources within these domains, as it is notably difficult to find appropriate keywords for the categories with the lowest levels of uniqueness, and the most overlap (Gusenbauer, 2022).

Despite these insights that the literature offers, there is a noticeable gap in the literature when researching the ASJC system. The vast majority of articles that pertain to the ASJC system are focused instead on Scopus itself, and mentions of the ASJC are incidental. While information and opinions about the ASJC can be gleaned by examining the ways in which it is used by Scopus, this is in many cases a poor substitute for a focused study on the ASJC itself. Ideally, as time goes on, more comprehensive research will be done on the ASJC as a standalone categorization system rather than merely as a defining feature of Scopus. While this report functions as an evaluation of the ASJC in comparison with the LCC, based on an independent study of the categorization system, further exploration by other researchers in the Library and Information Science (LIS) field will help to corroborate or refine these conclusions.

3 Evaluation

In this section, an evaluation of the ASJC system will be performed to determine its suitability for the DOAJ. Several methods were used to analyze the potential of the ASJC system. The classifications were mapped from the LCC to the ASJC system to determine if LCC classes could be matched with those from the ASJC system. A random sample of journals were also reclassified in order to determine how easy and accurate it would be to shift from the current classification system to a new one. Then, a random sample of classified journals from the DOAJ was taken and compared with their classification in Scopus using the ASJC system to determine how well Scopus-assigned ASJC codes aligned with the DOAJ's LCC classifications.

3.1 Analysis of the new classification system

The ASJC system is divided into four main hierarchies known as subject areas. These subject areas are: Physical Sciences, Health Sciences, Social Sciences & Humanities and Life Sciences. These are then divided into 27 subject area classifications. Each subject area classification is further divided into more granular subclassifications. The Physical Sciences contain the largest number of subclassifications at 115, followed by the Health Sciences with 102. The Social Sciences and Humanities are further divided into 65 classifications and the Life Sciences have 51. The ASJC system also has a multidisciplinary classification that comprises one subject area. A journal may be assigned to more than one subject area in Scopus. The ASJC system has only a handful more main classifications than the LCC system. The LCC system can get quite granular by assigning multiple letters and numbers to a

subclass. Meanwhile, the ASJC system does not appear to have that particular granularity, the deepest this system goes is to the subcategories for each subject area classification. While examining subject area classifications it became apparent that there was not an even distribution of subclasses. For example, the medicine subject area classification is divided into 49 subclasses while other subject area classifications are much less developed, some having as little as 4 subclassification options. This may hinder The DOAJ's ability to implement a new classification system because journals belonging to underdeveloped subject area classifications may be inaccurately represented.

Figure 1

Number of ASJC codes by subject area classification

As mentioned above and demonstrated by Figure 1, the ASJC codes are separated into 5 subject areas. However, it is interesting to note that the Physical Sciences and the Health Sciences have almost the same amount of codes despite the Physical Sciences having double

the amount of classes than the Health Sciences. There are only 5 classes under the Health Sciences (Medicine, Nursing, Veterinary, Dentistry and Health professions), yet it has the second highest number of codes. Subject areas with a similar number of classes, e. g. the Life Sciences and Social Sciences & Humanities with 5 and 6 classes respectively, have significantly less ASJC codes. This shows how overrepresented the Health Sciences are in the ASJC system and how this classification system is unbalanced and favours some subject areas over others.

Though the ASJC system does have many subcategories, they can be more general. This might make it difficult to classify journals with a very specific scope. It might also create some difficulties for researchers trying to find a journal in which to publish if their area of expertise is highly specialized. The ASJC system does cover many scholarly disciplines, especially those aligned to the sciences, which represent the majority of the subclassifications. This system could be used to classify journals in the DOAJ given its depth. However, some more specialized disciplines would have to be classified in a more general category. This could be beneficial, more so for someone who is searching for a journal and does not know the range of the discipline, but it could be disadvantageous for someone who already knows what they require. At first glance, the ASJC system does not seem optimal for the DOAJ because it is lacking in granularity, particularly in subjects that are not in the sciences. This lack would make it more difficult for researchers to find journals to read or in which to publish.

3.2 Mapping old to new classification system

One method used to try and ascertain the viability of changing the DOAJ's classification system was to map the LCC system into the ASJC classifications. The remapping process was deemed a viable option to try and reclassify the LCC system into ASJC as the ASJC system was deemed less complicated and had fewer bottom level classifications than the LCC. The truncated version of the LCC that the DOAJ uses has 3 levels of classification; 20 supertypes assigned one letter each, such as A for General Works, H for Social Sciences, and V for Naval Sciences. There are 153 subtypes that fit under these supertypes, identified by a second letter, and then a bottom level classification under the subtypes can be added, amounting to 450 options for classification in the LCC. This sums up to a total possible number of classifications being 523, as the DOAJ classified some journals using only a supertype or subtype instead of always using the bottom level. The ASJC system on the other hand divides their system up into 5 major subject areas, then assigns the first two digits of a 4-digit call number to the subject's field and the second two to the precise subject. For example, 2100 is *General Energy*, while 2103 is *Fuel Technology*. Health sciences have 102 subjects, life sciences have 51 subjects, physical sciences have 115 subjects, social sciences and humanities have 65 subjects, and the multidisciplinary major subject area stands as its own final categorization. This amounts to a grand total of 334 possible subject areas at the subject level, which is fewer than the 523 that the DOAJ's current LCC system has. Because of this, it is theoretically possible to put one or more of the 523 LCC classifications

in an appropriate ASJC subject. To that end we used excel to extract every unique LCC classification used for each journal in the DOAJ collection, then using a printed out copy of the complete list of Scopus subject areas, we reassigned each LCC classification to one appropriate ASJC classification.

Several issues with this process became apparent during its execution, however. The DOAJ only used 493 of the 523 possible unique LCC classifications for their indexed journals. Additionally, some of the LCC classifications did not have appropriate options within the ASJC subjects. For example, one or more journals in the DOAJ are classified under *Technology: Home economics: Cookery* in the LCC system, and the closest option the ASJC could provide was *Physical Sciences: Engineering (Miscellaneous)*. Other times the ASJC classifications were not specific enough to encapsulate certain LCC classifications, such as the entire supertype of V for Naval science which, although used by the DOAJ, was not specified any further in the LCC classification, resulting in them being unable to be classified appropriately by the ASJC system. Occasionally LCC classifications were too broad and had to be classified more than once within the ASJC, such as with *Science: Physics: Geophysics. Cosmic Physics*, which was classified as both *Physical sciences: Astronomy and Astrophysics*; and *Physical sciences: Space and Planetary Science*. Sometimes the fault lay with the ASJC system for being unable to reclassify into one subject; *Social Sciences & Humanities 1203* is *Arts and humanities: Language and Linguistics*, whereas *Social Sciences & Humanities 3310* is *Social Sciences: Linguistics and Languages*. The granularity presented between these two subject areas is too specific for many of the LCC classifications, resulting in both having to be mapped to several classifications. The remapping procedure was almost entirely feasible on a classifications level. Only 2% of the journals were left out, as they belonged to classes like *Military* or *Naval Science* and did not have an appropriate match in the ASJC. It would likely be possible to reclassify them individually at the journal level if the DOAJ decided to adopt the ASJC as their new classification system.

When the remapping process was completed, we were able to check how the assigned classifications operated on the DOAJ collection. There were 14,603 DOAJ journals that fell under *Social Sciences & Humanities*, 4,938 under *Physical Sciences*, 3,484 under *Life Sciences*, 3,746 under *Health Sciences*, and 497 that fell under categories that were either too general or did not have appropriate alternatives in ASJC. The *Multidisciplinary* subject was not used in the remapping process because it is not used consistently in the ASJC system and there was no appropriate way to reclassify LCC categories into it. The proportions of the DOAJ journals can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2

Proportion of DOAJ Journals by ASJC Major Subject Areas

This also allowed us to analyze the pattern regarding the number of journals in the individual bottom level classifications of the ASJC and compare them to the DOAJ. The most overrepresented LCC classifications in DOAJ are *Education (General)* at 1,319 journals, *Social Sciences: Commerce: Business* at 1,209, and *Medicine: Internal Medicine: Neurosciences, Biological Psychiatry. Neuropsychiatry* at 900 journals. From the reclassification into ASJC, the top three became more popular but shifted slightly. *Education* was still the most popular at 2,167, followed by *Language and Linguistics* at 1,506 and *General Business, Management and Accounting* at 1,289 journals. Broadly, both ASJC and LCC suffered from a lack of even distribution between their classifications, with popular and less granular classifications being overrepresented, but in slightly different ways. ASJC had more granularity in medical and science classifications than LCC, however it had less granularity in social sciences topics such as law, literature, humanities, and business - so the overall pattern remained unchanged.

3.3 Reclassifying journals

In order to assess the suitability of a new classification system for the DOAJ, a sample of 110 journals were reclassified using ASJC. These journals were selected randomly using a random number generator; if the link to the journal was not functional, a new random journal was chosen. Each journal's aims and scopes were analyzed to assess the aboutness of the journal. Once the aboutness was determined, the journal was classified using the ASJC system. Reclassification was limited to only one new class for the large majority of the journals. However, some journals with a multidisciplinary scope were assigned to two top level classes. Most randomly selected journals (53 %) were able to be classified into a

suitable category in the ASJC system, meaning that the class well reflected the journal’s aims and scopes [Figure 3]. For example, a journal on the subject of cardiology was able to be suitably reclassified into ASJC’s class 2705 *Cardiology and Cardiovascular Medicine*. However, a large portion (29 %) of journals could not be sorted into a suitable category. This was mostly due to there being no category that accurately represented the journal’s subject matter. In these cases, journal’s were classified in a broader category, usually in the “General” category of a subclass, which can be problematic if the journal does have a specific scope but must be classified more generally because no other accurate classification code can be assigned.

Figure 3

Suitability of Reclassification With ASJC Code From a Random Sample of Journals

Classifying journals under a general category is problematic because these journals do not possess a general scope and it would hinder researcher’s ability to find a suitable journal in the DOAJ. In comparison with the LCC system, the ASJC offers less granularity and some categories simply do not exist. For example, one sampled journal’s scope was design, but ASJC does not have a design category. The journal was classified in the *Visual Arts and Performing Arts* category, however this is not the most representative class for a design journal. Some journal classifications using ASJC were determined to be acceptable (18 %). This option represents journals whose ASJC classification was somewhat representative of their aims and scope, but not entirely suitable. However, this option is not optimal because classification should aim to be as representative as possible. The acceptable classifications mostly occurred when a journal had a very broad scope and thus should be in multiple categories. For example, one journal’s scope mentioned several topics related to philosophy

as well as ethics, epistemology and history of philosophy. It was assigned the classification of *Philosophy* under the ASJC system, however, the journal's many topics makes this assignment quite general. In this case multiple classifications should be assigned, but the DOAJ limits two classifications per journal. For this journal, and many others, two codes may not be enough, which is why a more granular classification system would be more beneficial to the DOAJ.

Figure 4

Number of Journals That Were Suitable, Unsuitable or Acceptable in Each ASJC Top-level Class

ASJC Top Level Class	Suitable	Unsuitable	Acceptable	Total Journals Reclassified
Agricultural and Biological Sciences	2	2	1	5
Arts and Humanities	4	4	5	13
Arts and Humanities; Social Sciences	1		1	2
Business, Management and Accounting	3		1	4
Chemistry	1			1
Computer Science; Engineering; Mathematics			1	1
Earth and Planetary Sciences	3		1	4
Economics, Econometrics and Finance	5			5
Energy			1	1
Engineering	1	1	1	3
Environmental Science		1	1	2
Health Professions	1			1
Materials Science		1		1
Mathematics	2	3		5
Medicine	16	6		22
Medicine; Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology		1		1
Multidisciplinary	2	6		8
Nursing	1	1	1	3
Physics and Astronomy	1			1
Psychology		1	1	2
Social Sciences	14	7	3	24
Veterinary	1			1
Grand total				110

Figure 4 shows which top level classifications have the most amount of suitable journal reclassifications. In the ASJC system, the medicine classification contains the most subclasses. Because of its many subclasses, the journals that fell under the medicine category were able to be classified more accurately than most other categories. This is also true for the second largest category, the social sciences. However, when attempting to classify a journal in a smaller category, for example the arts and humanities, the new classifications were mostly acceptable or unsuitable. These findings show the ASJC system's bias towards the sciences, which can be problematic when replacing the DOAJ's current classification system because the DOAJ is home to journals across many different disciplines and thus, they require accurate classification. There were also instances in which reclassification could be possible in two top level classes of the ASJC system. Reclassification in more than one class was used only when necessary. That being said, it is possible to have more than one top level class in the DOAJ system, which could increase the suitability of the ASJC system for the

DOAJ. However, given the sizable portion of unsuitable reclassifications, The ASJC system may not be the best fit for the DOAJ's needs.

3.4 Identifying classified journals

As of May 2022, Scopus has over 5,000 Open Access journals in their database, all classified using the ASJC scheme. Many of these journals were also classified in the DOAJ database, using their truncated version of the LCC. To assess how differently each system classified journals in a real application, a sample of 100 journals available in both databases was selected. Journals were randomly selected from Scopus's source file, which is available for public download with a user account and is available in the form of an excel spreadsheet. The journals were filtered to only include those journals which were open access and a random number generator was used to identify and select the journals used for the sample. In cases where journals were not available in both databases, a new article was randomly selected in its place.

The classes assigned according to each database and classification scheme were qualitatively assessed to examine how well DOAJ classifications using LCC matched Scopus classifications using ASJC. The results of the qualitative assessment are shown in Figure 5. Match level was determined based on how closely the concepts in ASJC classes aligned with those of the LCC. As previously established, Scopus is very liberal in its assignment of classifications. As such, some sources had 2 or more classifications, with the largest number of classifications for a single journal in the random sample being 8. In cases where multiple classes were assigned, all assigned classes were examined to determine match level to LCC classifications as assigned by the DOAJ. Items were determined to have a low level of matching if there was little conceptual or semantic overlap between ASJC and LCC classifications, or in cases where the ASJC required several codes to match LCC's single classifications. For example, in one case, the journal "Vertebrate Zoology" was classified under the subclass *Zoology* in LCC and was classified under the subclass *Ecology, Evolution, Behaviour and Systematics* in ASJC. In this case there is not much overlap between these classes. Given that the journal topic is zoology and that ASJC has a classification code for animal science and zoology specifically, this case may simply be an error with Scopus's database and may not directly reflect ASJC in terms of classification capabilities.

Conversely, journals were determined to have exact, high, or moderate levels of matching between classification systems if there was conceptual or semantic overlap between classes. The higher the overlap, the higher the match level. For example, a journal classified under the subclass *Gynecology and Obstetrics* in LCC was also classified under the subclass *Obstetrics and Gynecology* in ASJC. In this case, both subclasses are semantically and conceptually equivalent and thereby were determined to be an exact match. High matches were those that were very similar, but not exact. Moderate matches were those that had somewhat similar conceptual overlap in their classifications, but ultimately were not the best fit. For example, a journal about vision was classified in the DOAJ under *Science: Biology (General)*, and in Scopus under the life science subclasses of *Cell Biology, Cognitive*

Neuroscience, and *Neurology* as well as the health sciences subclasses of *Optometry* and *Ophthalmology*. In this case, there is some overlap in that both systems selected some aspect of biology for the classification, but the ASJC had 6 codes assigned and had more granular classifications available.

Figure 5

Level of Matching Between ASJC and LCC Classifications of Common Journals Available in Both Scopus and DOAJ

As demonstrated in Figure 5 above, 71% of journals examined had a moderate to exact match between ASJC and LCC classifications, leaving only 20% with a moderate match and 9% with a low match. In 33.3% of cases where the match level between classifications was low, ASJC outperformed LCC significantly. These were cases in which the topic of the journal was too contemporary for LCC to handle well. For example, one journal about computer data and networking was classified under the subclass *Industrial Management* in LCC. In ASJC, however, the journal was assigned to the following classes: *Artificial Intelligence*; *Computer Networks and Communications*; *Computer Science Applications*; *Communication*; *Information Systems*; *Software*. While the subclass *Computer Networks and Communications* would have been sufficient on its own to classify this journal, this is another case in which the Scopus database is more at fault than the scheme itself. It is clear, however, that ASJC handles contemporary and computer-based topics much better than does LCC.

However, the opposite is true for journals that fell under the Arts & Humanities disciplines, where LCC far outperformed ASJC. For example, the journal *Lexis*, which focuses on English lexicology, was classified under the subclasses *Linguistics and Language* and *Language and Linguistics* in ASJC. However, under LCC, the same journal was classified under the subclasses *Language* and *Lexicography*. In this case, not only are ASJC's

classifications severely lacking in granularity, but they are also confusing in that two separate classifications that are nearly identical were assigned.

Based on this qualitative analysis, it is evident that ASJC outperforms LCC in contemporary, technology and life science-oriented classifications. However, LCC significantly outperforms ASJC in subjects pertaining to arts & humanities disciplines.

4 Recommendation and adoption

While it is evident that the LCC system is rife with problems, and likely unsuitable for long-term use in the DOAJ without adjustment, the ASJC system is not an appropriate replacement and we thereby do not recommend its implementation. The mapping showed an uneven distribution of classifications with classes like medicine being overrepresented and others such as arts and humanities having significantly less classes. As demonstrated in the process of reclassifying journals in the DOAJ using ASJC codes, only a little over half of the journals examined were easily and accurately reclassified. A large portion of journals sampled from the DOAJ did not have accurate or appropriate classifications under the ASJC system, which would present a major issue when migrating from the LCC to ASJC. As found throughout all stages of our evaluation, the ASJC is disproportionately granular in life and health sciences categories, and significantly lacking in granularity in the arts and humanities. Across all phases of evaluation (remapping, reclassifying, and identification of classified journals), this unevenness in granularity presented notable issues. During the reclassification and the identification of classified journals, it became evident that the ASJC relies on multiple classifications per journal to accurately classify journals — one class code was generally not enough on its own.

However, the ASJC was able to perform well in certain areas. In the case of identifying classified journals in Scopus and in the DOAJ, Scopus' classifications using ASJC were often more accurate than those assigned in the DOAJ, particularly in contemporary fields of study with a focus on technology. ASJC class codes tackle such contemporary topics much better than does the LCC, likely because of how much more recently the ASJC was developed. However, these improvements on their own are not enough for the ASJC to be considered a viable alternative to the DOAJ's current system.

The ASJC's issues with granularity and a lopsided focus on sciences mean that it cannot appropriately represent the full scope of the publications represented in the DOAJ. There certainly are aspects of the ASJC system that should ideally be found in whichever replacement is eventually chosen, such as more granularity in fields like medicine and dentistry. However, these particular improvements cannot justify the large undertaking and dedication of time and resources for replacing the LCC system. This is especially the case since the number of suitable replacements for journal categorization are far lower than would merit such a change. Moving forward, we recommend that the decision-makers at the DOAJ have established priorities for which classes require the greatest degree of granularity, and select a classification system accordingly.

The ideal classification system for the DOAJ would be one that was developed more recently and can handle the classification of complex, interdisciplinary and contemporary topics. The new system should ideally have a consistent level of granularity across disciplines and should be developed with the context of a diverse and globalized society in mind. Because the DOAJ accepts journals from around the world, in a variety of disciplines and languages, a classification system that was designed with diversity from a global perspective in mind would be ideal. As evidenced by the LCC, classification systems that are time-bound or specific to a certain culture or the region in which they were developed are not able to handle diverse materials without significant bias. Perhaps the most glaring issue with the LCC is its 19th-century American perspective, so choosing a classification system that is not bound by biases in this way is likely the best approach for a directory which accepts journals from around the globe.

5 Conclusion

The process of assessing the suitability of the ASJC system for the DOAJ revealed both a great deal of relevant information, and avenues towards which future research may be directed. While there is no shortage of articles arguing the inadequacies with the LCC system, there is an undeniable gap in the literature for studies which evaluate the ASJC system on its own merits, rather than merely as a corollary to the Scopus database. While this study may go some ways to remedying this, more research into what uses (beyond Scopus) the ASJC system may have, and how best to adapt it to the most relevant databases, would be of great value. We do not recommend the ASJC system for the reasons detailed above, namely a lopsided granularity which favours the sciences and the inability to appropriately classify many of the journals in the DOAJ. While the ASJC classification system handles contemporary topics better than does the LCC, we do not consider these benefits to be numerous enough to justify the resource expenditure needed for the DOAJ to entirely change its classification system. However, many of the aforementioned advantages which the ASJC system (namely its modern outlook, compared to a turn-of-the-century system) should be looked for in any other potential replacement. Ideally, this assessment will aid the decision-makers at the DOAJ and any individuals designing classification systems to set their priorities as to what features are of the greatest value in a new classification system.

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